

MULTISCALE MODELING OF THERMOSET COMPOSITE TO PREDICT PROCESS-INDUCED RESIDUAL STRESSES

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ABSTRACT

A novel multi-scale Integrated Computational Material Engineering (ICME) approach to predict the evolution of residual stress during curing of thermoset composites is presented. Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations and Finite Element Analysis (FEA) are used at their respective length scales to determine the cure induced effect on thermoset fiber-reinforced composites. First, curing is simulated at the molecular level to predict the density (shrinkage), Young's modulus, and yield strength as a function of the degree of cure. Second, the correlation between polymer properties and tensile transverse strength is obtained by modeling the residual stress build-up at the micro-scale. Preliminary results are presented for EPON 862/DETDA epoxy system at the nano-scale. Stress evolution during curing is modeled at the micro-scale using five randomly packed 18-fiber Repeating Unit Cells (RUCs) with IM7 carbon fibers, and the predicted composite transverse strength results are presented. Finally, a theoretical framework for future work is outlined.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer Matrix Composites (PMCs) are advanced materials used in aerospace engineering applications because of their desirable-specific properties such as high strength/weight and stiffness/weight ratios that are not fully exploited yet. Among PMCs, thermosets are a class of polymers that undergo chemical reactions when subjected to pressure and temperature, causing polymer chains to cross-link and form a material that gradually can sustain stress. When thermosets start to solidify, or "cure", self-equilibrated stresses begin building up. A better understanding of the curing process of thermosets is needed to optimize currently used material systems, create new and more performant resins, minimize energy consumption during manufacturing and reduce composites production costs. Composite mechanical properties are determined by phenomena that occur at different length scales during manufacturing: polymer chains crosslink at the molecular level, fibers affect the matrix behavior at the micro-scale determining matrix "in-situ" properties. The final microstructure configuration drives composites performance at the macro-scale. Material characterization across the scales is a labor intense and time-consuming task. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), Thermomechanical Analysis (TMA) and mechanical testing are needed to characterize the resin as a function of the crosslinking process. Integrated Computational Materials Engineering (ICME) multi-scale approaches are preferred tools in the effort to reduce the material and process development cycle time and cost for future high-technology applications of PMCs [1-5]. For a particular fiber-matrix laminate system, the optimal cure cycle can be computationally identified such that the cured product has the highest strength and stiffness.

This work describes a novel virtual testing procedure that, starting from the chemical structure of thermoset polymers, fiber properties and curing temperature profile, is able to predict stiffness and strength of PMCs. This approach is based on a multi-scale method that focuses on two-scales. First, Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations are performed at the nanoscale to determine the thermo-mechanical properties of curing resin as a function of the degree of cure. Then, virtually-characterized resin properties are used in a Finite Element Analysis (FEA) in which PMCs are modeled through Repeating Unit Cells (RUCs) at the micro-scale to characterize the composite transverse tensile

composite mechanical properties. MD simulation methods were originally developed within the field of theoretical physics and then extended to the analysis of biomolecules, chemistry, and material science [6]. The remarkable advances in High-Performance Computing (HPC) made this method particularly suitable for ICME studies and analysis of nanocomposites [7, 8]. A significant amount of research has been performed on the MD modeling of thermosetting polymer resins with respect to the degree of cure [7, 9-16]. These works use various techniques to control the relative amount of crosslinking within the thermoset framework. Although these studies have demonstrated that the MD simulation can be effectively used to relate the degree of cure to molecular-scale properties, this information has never been used in a multiscale-modeling framework to examine the relationship between the degree of cure and bulk-level properties. Recent work established that numerical studies can be performed to virtually reproduce curing at the micro-scale assuming that the mechanical response of the composite material can be obtained by studying RUCs [5, 17-19]. Curing models for the stress evolution during curing have been described in the literature [17-20]. Recent work by Maiarù et al. outlined the procedure for the mechanical characterization of all strengths and stiffnesses of thin transversely isotropic laminae using FEA at the micro-scale [19]. Building upon recent developments in MD and micromechanics simulations, the following sections propose an integrated approach between nano- and micro-scale modeling.

This paper is organized as follows: nano- and micro-scale modeling procedures are respectively detailed in Section 2. Preliminary results are presented in Section 3. A theoretical framework for future work is detailed in Section 4.

2 MODELING APPROACH

The proposed method is a two-scale approach. First, the polymer is virtually cured within MD simulations at the nano-scale. Subsequently, MD results in terms of degree of crosslinking and matrix mechanical properties as a function of curing are used as inputs into FE models at the micro-scale. At the micro-level, Repeating Unit Cells (RUCs) are first virtually cured to predict the residual stress build up; then RUCs undergo simulated tensile mechanical loading in the transverse direction. The analysis is performed in three subsequent steps as depicted in Figure 1. In Step I, MD simulations are used to characterize the mechanical properties of the polymer as a function of the degree of crosslinking during curing. In Step II, the simulations of the residual stress build-up are performed. Finally, in Step III, the virtual tensile testing in the transverse direction is performed to characterize composite mechanical properties at the micro-scale.

Figure 1: Two-scale approach procedure. From left to right: Step I - Molecular Dynamics Simulations; Step II - virtual curing of composite microstructures and Step III - mechanical testing of virtually cured Representative Unit Cells at the micro-scale.

2.1 Molecular Dynamics Modeling

Figure 2 shows an example of network formations during curing for a representative chunk of

epoxy that, for sake of simplicity in explaining the model, contains just three networks that progressively form at time t_1 (network 1), t_2 (network 2) and t_3 (network 3). The large and small spheres represent the amount of epoxy and hardener that will crosslink during curing. The three independent networks are depicted with solid blue, green and grey lines. At time t_1 , the first network forms in a stress-free configuration. Chemical shrinkage is also observed at the end of curing.

MD methods used to determine the influence of crosslink density on the mechanical properties of the epoxy system (EPON 862/DETDA) are described below. The LAMMPS (Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator) software package is used for all MD simulations described herein [1, 21].

To perform the epoxide-amine crosslinking reactions, high-energy bonds are created as an initial step. To ensure that the epoxy molecular structure is not inadvertently damaged upon network formation, all epoxy models are initially built using the OPLS (Optimized Potentials for Liquid Simulations) all-atom force field [22]. Since OPLS is a fixed-bond force field, all other bonds will remain intact when large energy spikes are introduced in the system. It is expected that creating high-energy bonds in ReaxFF [24] would result in unintended dissociation of neighboring bonds. First, the monomers are arrayed sparsely in a periodic simulation box. A fixed-volume simulation of 100 ps is performed to allow the monomers to mix, in which the temperature is gradually ramped down from 327 °C to 27 °C. Following these mixing simulations, the simulation boxes are slowly compressed to densities of 1.21 g/cm³. These simulations occurred at 27 °C for a total of 4 ns, and 20 molecular minimizations were performed at regular intervals during the process. The simulated monomer crosslinking process is described in detail elsewhere [23]. A total of seven models were established, with crosslink densities (defined as the number of crosslinks formed with respect to the total number of potential reactive sites) of 54, 58, 71, 77, 82, 84, and 85%. Once the crosslinks were formed, the force field was switched to the reactive force field ReaxFF [24] because of its ability to capture bond scission (and thus material failure) during mechanical deformation, with the low-gradient corrected ReaxFF parameters of Liu et al. [25] The Liu et al. parameter set was selected since it contains the required elements for modeling epoxide and amine groups, demonstrates improved van der Waals interactions for solids, and has been shown to provide reliable results for determining the elastic moduli and yield points of epoxies [26]. Further details on the force field switching process may be found elsewhere [24]. Equilibration occurred over 1.5 ns at 27 °C. Using the NPT ensemble (constant pressure and temperature), the Nose-Hoover barostat is set to maintain 0.101 MPa (1 atm) of pressure on all sides of the simulation box. A time step of 0.1 fs is used. The resulting mass densities closely matched experimental values [22].

After establishing the equilibrated models, each model is subjected to three uniaxial tensile deformation simulations: tension in the x -, y -, and z -directions. Deformations are performed every timestep amounting to 20% engineering strain over 1 ns, resulting in a strain rate of 2×10^8 s⁻¹. In the transverse directions, the Nose-Hoover barostat is assigned to maintain 0.101 MPa (1 atm) of pressure to enable Poisson contractions. A time step of 0.1 fs and a temperature of 27 °C is specified.

Figure 2: Simplified example of Epoxy resin containing just 3 networks (polymer chains) that form one at the time respectively at t_1 , t_2 , and t_3 to explain the crosslink formation mechanisms.

2.2 Micromechanics

Mechanical properties as a function of the degree of crosslinking are needed to predict the curing induced residual stress build-up in thermoset composites. Various models have been defined to represent cure based on the stress evolution and material shrinkage. In this work, an instantaneous linear elastic model (Equation 1) is used to predict the residual stress build up during cure as described in the work by Maiarù et al. [19]:

$$\sigma_i(t) = [C_{ij}(t)] [\varepsilon_j^t(t) - (\varepsilon_j^{th}(t) + \varepsilon_j^c(t)) \delta_j] \quad (1)$$

where, i and j are Voigt notation indices and $\varepsilon^t(t)$, $\varepsilon^{th}(t)$ and $\varepsilon^c(t)$ are the total, thermal and curing shrinkage strains respectively. $C_{ij}(t)$ is the stiffness matrix as a function of the time of cure and δ_j is:

$$\delta_j = \begin{cases} 1, & j = 1, 2, 3 \\ 0, & j > 3 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Residual stress evolution as a function of the degree of crosslinking is implemented as a user-written subroutine (UMAT) within the commercially available FE software Abaqus. The finite element model is represented by a square RUC with randomly packed fibers. A randomized RUC generator algorithm developed in MATLAB by Carey et al. [27] is used to create models of composite micro-structures which, given the fiber diameter $d_f = 6\mu\text{m}$, fiber volume fraction $v_f = 55\%$, and the number of fibers $n_f = 18$, can generate different realizations. The pre-processing in Abaqus, which is automated through Python scripting, includes importing the fiber coordinates from the RUC generator and creating the mesh and the boundary conditions for the finite element model. RUC size convergence has been performed to identify the minimum number of fibers needed to represent the correct composite mechanical behavior in term of transverse stress and stiffness. The thickness of these RUC is restricted to $1\mu\text{m}$ for the plane stress assumption. Each RUC is meshed with C3D8RT elements (eight-node brick elements with reduced integration and temperature degrees of cure). The fibers are modeled as transversely isotropic solids whose properties are listed in Table 1, while the matrix material is modeled as isotropic. Five RUCs have been studied to account for variability in stress concentration due to fiber random distributions as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Five 18-fiber randomly packed RUC models.

Thermal properties used in analysis			
Epoxy 862		IM7 Carbon Fiber	
$\alpha^m (mm/mm - K)$	$61e - 6$	$\alpha_{11}^f (mm/mm - K)$	$-0.54e - 6$
$k^m (mW/mm - K)$	0.2	$\alpha_{22}^f (mm/mm - K)$	$10.08e - 6$
$C_p^m (mJ/tonne - K)$	$1.2e9$	$k^f (mW/mm - K)$	5.4
		$C_p^f (mJ/tonne - K)$	$0.879e9$

Table 1: Thermal material properties for epoxy resin and carbon fibers used in the analysis, including the thermal expansion coefficient α , conductivity k , and heat capacity c_p .

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preliminary results from MD simulations and their integration within the proposed FEA approach are discussed hereafter. Stress-strain plots were analyzed for each MD deformation simulation. The true stress and true strain were calculated in the axial direction. To obtain Young's modulus, the stress-strain plot was fitted with a linear regression model for strains up to about 3%. A moving average was calculated to smooth the scattered stress-strain data typical of MD models at finite temperatures [22]. The smoothing allowed for a more precise determination of the yield point. The yield point was defined as the location where the smoothed stress-strain curve crossed the 0.2% offset line.

In Figure 4, Young's modulus is plotted with respect to the crosslink density. Each data point indicates the mean Young's modulus of one model. The standard deviation is deduced from three uniaxial tensile simulations. For the crosslinked systems studied, there is no clear effect of crosslink density on the modulus. However, because the modulus approaches zero as the crosslink density approaches zero (the polymer is in liquid form at zero crosslink density), the intermediate modulus values can be estimated, as shown in Figure 4. Figure 5 shows the yield stress versus crosslink density. Each data point indicates the average yield stress from deforming an individual epoxy model in three directions. The MD simulations predicted the average Poisson's ratio to be 0.37 ± 0.05 . All of these predicted values demonstrate excellent agreement with experiment [23].

The thermal properties used in the cure analysis for the resin and IM7 carbon fibers are detailed in Table 1. The mechanical properties of the fully solidified resin have been modeled based on experimental results. The mechanical response of the RUC is affected by the prescribed set of Boundary Conditions (BC) for curing (Step II) and for subsequent mechanical loading (Step III). During the cure analysis (Step II), the boundaries of the RUC are allowed to expand or contract depending on the temperature change. Further contraction due to shrinkage is also modeled assuming a final shrinkage of 2% and constant coefficient of thermal expansion throughout curing listed in Table 1. Flat Boundary Conditions (FBC) are applied so that parallel faces of the undeformed RUC remain parallel post curing as shown in Figure 1, Step II. The *EQUATION card in Abaqus is used to prescribe the FBC that pairs the movement of the nodes on each face of the RUC with a significant reference point on the cross-section. Results from the transverse tension virtual tests for the five random realizations are reported in Figure 6. Scattering in mechanical properties is due to different

stress concentrations induced by fiber proximity in the five randomly packed RUCs.

Figure 4: Young's modulus of epoxy predicted from MD simulations, with a power-law extrapolation to zero crosslink density.

Figure 5: Yield strength of epoxy predicted from MD simulations, with a linear extrapolation to zero crosslink density.

Figure 6: Yield strength of epoxy predicted from MD simulations, with a linear extrapolation to zero crosslink density.

4 STRAIN RATE EFFECT

The measured elastic, strength and fracture properties of polymer materials are generally dependent on the applied strain rate. The elastic modulus dependence on strain rate is mostly due to the viscoelastic nature of polymers [28]. The dependence of strength and fracture on strain rate is due to both the viscoelastic response as well as the complex failure mechanisms that occur on multiple length scales in polymers [29].

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations are computationally demanding and can only simulate phenomena on very small times scales (nanoseconds). If an MD simulation includes a simulated deformation of a material (e.g. uniaxial tension) to predict a mechanical property, the deformation must occur on the order of nanoseconds. Under typical laboratory conditions, experimental mechanical testing occurs over much higher time scales, such as seconds, minutes, or hours. Thus, the time scales of MD simulations and experimental testing differ by several orders of magnitude, as does their corresponding strain rates. Therefore, it is expected that predicted and measured mechanical properties should also differ significantly. This discrepancy is typically referred to as the *strain rate effect*.

Odegard et al. [26] first quantified the strain rate effect for a DGEBF (Diglycidyl ether of Bisphenol F) epoxy system with a DETDA (Diethylene Toluene Diamine) hardener. MD simulations were used to predict the elastic modulus and yield strength of this epoxy system at two strain rates: $1 \times 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $2 \times 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}$. These properties were compared to experimentally-measured modulus and yield strength values on the same material system reported by Littell et al. [30] at three strain rates: $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and $2 \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Thus the strain rates differed by as much as thirteen orders of magnitude. These comparisons of modulus and strength showed a significant discrepancy between measurements and predictions, but they also showed a clear scaling law of the properties due to the strain rate effect.

Radue and Odegard [31] used MD simulation to predict the elastic modulus of epoxy/CNT nanocomposites and compared the results to experimental measurements from the literature for a range of CNT volume fractions. They demonstrated excellent agreement between predictions and measurements when the modulus values were normalized with respect to the modulus values at 0% CNT volume fraction. In effect, this normalization mitigated the strain rate effect by canceling out the corresponding error from the values. Thus, normalization is a very convenient way of minimizing the error in predicted mechanical property values due to the strain rate effect.

As an example, the measured and predicted values of elastic modulus of epoxy can be normalized with respect to a fixed value at degree of cure $\phi=1$ and temperature $T=300\text{K}$. Similar to the assumption of Radue and Odegard [31], we can assume that the normalized values between experiment and simulation are equal:

$$\frac{E_{actual}(\phi, T)}{E_{exp}(\phi=1, T=300K)} = \frac{E_{MD}(\phi, T)}{E_{MD}(\phi=1, T=300K)} \quad (3)$$

Where, E_{actual} is the actual modulus of the polymer at the specified conditions of ϕ and T (to be used in upper length scale calculations), E_{exp} is the benchmarked experimental value at $\phi=1$ and $T=300\text{K}$, and E_{MD} is the predicted value from molecular dynamics at the specified conditions of ϕ and T . Equation (3) can be rearranged to

$$E_{actual}(\phi, T) = \frac{E_{exp}(\phi=1, T=300K)}{E_{MD}(\phi=1, T=300K)} E_{MD}(\phi, T) \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) is convenient for minimizing the strain rate effect and relating modulus predictions from MD to the corresponding large time-scale properties for use in finite element modeling. Equations of the same form can be used for any properties that exhibit a strain rate effect. The choice of $\phi=1$ and $T=300\text{K}$ is made here for convenience since these conditions are relatively easy to achieve experimentally.

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